

Perceived Impact of Training Programmes for Academic Staff Development in Tertiary Institutions in Delta State

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Abstract

This study assessed the perceived impact of training programme for academic staff development in tertiary institutions in Delta state. Four research questions were answered, while, two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. A descriptive design was adopted. The population of this study was made up of three thousand, one hundred and forty-five (3,145) academic staff of eleven tertiary institutions in Delta State while the sample for this study comprised four hundred and seventy-two (472) academic staff of eleven Federal and State tertiary institutions in Delta State. The instrument for data collection was a researchers constructed close-ended questionnaire which was validated and tested. Analyses were based on four hundred and forty-four (444) properly filled questionnaires and was done using frequency, percentage, mean and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Statistics. Findings from the study revealed amongst others that the various training programmes for academic staff development in tertiary institutions in Delta state are master and doctorate degrees, mentorship, seminar, workshop, conference etc; training programmes had perceived impacted on academic staff in tertiary institution by improving their teaching and research skills, confidence during lectures; there was a relationship between sex, finance and participation of academic staff in training programme. Based on the findings from the study, it was concluded that training programmes designed for the development of academic staff have potential for capacity development and improvement in the productivity level. The study recommended that management of tertiary institutions should sustain the training programmes for academic staff development.

Keywords: Academic, Staff, Training, Programmes, Tertiary, Institutions

Introduction

Training is basically a practical education through which knowledge and skills are developed and inefficiencies are overcome. Realizing the value of training, human resource specialists have made deliberate decisions to encourage employers to give employees significant autonomy to develop their skills. They have also made a wide range of training available across their organisations, tailored to meet employee needs. To meet the current and future challenges of organisations, training encompasses a wide range of learning actions, from training individuals for their current tasks to sharing knowledge to enhance the organisation's capabilities and customer service. Training is a set of processes aimed at continuously enlightening employees' knowledge and skills, as well as organisational systems (Toriola, Gaito, Asiimwe & Kayindu, 2023). It is a learning activity to acquire the knowledge and skills needed to perform a task.

Training and development are important for any organisation's future because they provide employees with the skills and knowledge they need to be successful in their roles. By investing in training and development, organisations can ensure that their employees are able to meet the ever-changing demands of the workplace. Organisations need to be proactive in providing training and development opportunities for their employees. Giving employees the chance to enhance their skills and knowledge increases their engagement and productivity in their roles. Additionally, by providing training and development opportunities, organisations can attract and retain top talents. There are a variety of training and development programmes available, so organisations should select those that best fit their needs. Some common types of training and development programmes include classroom instruction, on-the-job training, mentorship programmes, and e-learning courses. The benefits of investing in training and development programmes are clear. By providing employees with the skills they need to be successful, organisations can create a more engaged workforce that is better equipped to meet the challenges of the future (Adeniji, Babalola & Adeniji, 2018).

The sole focus of workforce training is to develop an employee's specific skills for their specific job roles. Often, when an employee needs to step up to a new role or lead a group, he needs to go through a next-level learning experience to be more competent in his role-playing. Training programmes solve these obstacles and give employees a much-needed competitive advantage in the present market scenario. Training can be delivered in a lecture format or through more interactive methods like case

studies or role-playing. Online training is a convenient way to deliver instruction and can be accessed anytime, anywhere. Both new and existing employees can utilize it. On-the-job training involves shadowing experienced employees or learning through trial and error under close supervision. The training's objectives are to optimize human resource utilization, develop skills and productivity, and improve organizational culture.

In tertiary institutions, training encompasses several activities meant for staff development. The goal of staff development is to assist employees in acquiring the fundamental skills necessary for the effective performance of their assigned tasks or roles. It deals with the activities undertaken to expose an employee to perform additional duties and assume positions of importance in the organisation. Staff development is a crucial component of the development process, focusing on the acquisition of skills relevant to their respective professions. While development is essential for workers, it is even more crucial for academic staff in Delta State, Nigeria because they are the torchbearers of tertiary institutions. This justifies the constant emphasis on academic staff development programmes, which are now mandatory for upward mobility. Academic staff development is a process by which every educational institution develops, enhances, and improves its academic staff' skills, competencies, and overall performance. Academic staff development provides lecturers with information, skills, and an understanding of the school and its goals. It also encourages them to continue to make the necessary positive contribution to the institution's success in terms of their job performance.

Staff development programmes play a crucial role in constantly renewing, upgrading, updating, refreshing, and keeping academic staff abreast of a rapidly changing society. According to Gani (2019), the functions of staff in tertiary institutions are not only multiple but also continuously changing in modern societies. Academic staff development programmes can be formal and non-formal. The formal education programmes lead to the awards of degrees which includes Masters and Doctoral programmes, while the non-formal programmes are organized to educate, instruct and sensitise participants on certain aspects of their jobs. Certificates may be awarded depending on the nature of the programme. Programmes in this category include study-fellowship, orientation, induction, in-service training, conference, workshop, seminars, mentoring and so on.

Academic staff development programmes are very necessary for the self-efficacy of members of staff as well as the advancement of the institution and the society at large. However, without participation

in these programmes, the resources invested into these programmes will be wasted and the aim of these programmes would be defeated. In other words, active participation of academic staff in development programmes organized for them must be given adequate attention (Ogbu, Ojo & Ozah, 2018). There are certain factors that tend to affect their participation in development programmes, some of them are sex, finance, educational status, professional experience, attitudes and so on.

Sex of an individual is also seen as a factor in the performance of the individual in staff development programmes. For instance, the willingness to travel to distant locations for training programmes like conferences and seminars differ among males and females. The issue of domestic roles of women, like meal preparation, child care, home management amongst others, may affect their disposition to participate in training programmes especially when it is impromptu in nature. However, in recent times there has been a steady convergence on the difference between staff job performance as a result of gender difference. There seem to be a growing understanding that sex does not play any serious role in the performance of a staff in most roles except those that are very physical in nature.

Finance is an important aspect of staff development in educational institutions that the Federal Government declared in its National Policy on Education, “that teacher education and re-training will continue to be given a major emphasis in the nation’s educational planning, as no education system can rise above the quality of its teachers” (FGN, 2004). In view of this, several initiatives have been put in place for the development of lecturers in tertiary institutions by government, the administrators of tertiary institutions as well as support from other organisations. Government funded initiatives include sponsorship of staff development programmes through the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) and United Nations Educational Scientific Organisation (UNESCO) interventions (Yakubu, 2020). These government-funded staff development programmes are made available to academic staff of tertiary institutions in Nigeria including Delta State.

The number of tertiary institutions in Delta State implies that there is high demand for higher education in the State. To this extent therefore, there is need to ensure that these institutions are properly positioned to achieve its objective of ensuring human capacity development both for self and societal growth and development. Since lecturers are at the forefront of providing higher or tertiary education to students, it becomes paramount to ensure that they are well equipped to handle the assignments given

to them. It is against this background that this study seeks to assess the impact of training programmes for academic staff development in tertiary institutions in Delta state.

Statement of the Problem

Training programmes have become necessary in tertiary institutions because of lecturers' development and job performance which have necessitated the introduction of policies to encourage staff development. The main objective of the policy is to enable staff improve their qualifications in any area of study directly relevant to their primary assignment and also provide opportunity for staff to develop transferable skills and ability. To this extent, lecturers are provided opportunities of being sponsored for further education, seminars, workshops and conferences.

Despite the opportunities put in place for staff development, there are continuous complaints from parents and other stakeholders including students on the quality of some of the lecturers and their job performance, as it relates to poor content delivery, poor lecturing etiquette and commitment which seems to raise certain questions about the provision and effectiveness of the training programmes for academic staff development. Could it be that the lecturers are not disposed to academic training programmes, or is that the lecturers cannot assess training programmes. Could it also be that the lecturers are not effectively participating in the training programmes, and what could possibly be the cause or factors affecting lecturers' participation in training programmes for staff development. These and many other issues are considered very germane and necessitating attention.

Secondly, to the best of the researcher's knowledge, there is scarcity of empirical literature bordering on assessment of training programme for academic staff development in tertiary institutions in Delta State as majority of similar empirical works have focused on the attitude of trainees towards training programmes, level of involvement of trainees in training programmes and even determinants of participation in training programme, training and staff welfare, factors influencing participation in staff development programme. This has obviously created a gap in literature which must be filled. Hence the problem of this study was to assess the impact of training programmes for academic staff development in tertiary institutions in Delta state.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The main aim of this study is to assess the impact of training programmes for academic staff development in tertiary in Delta State. Specifically, this study seeks to;

1. find out the various training programmes for academic staff development in tertiary institutions in Delta State.
2. determine the perceived impact of training on academic staff in tertiary institutions in Delta State
3. find out if there is any relationship between sex and participation of academic staff in training for academic staff development in tertiary institutions in Delta State.
4. find out if there is any relationship between finance and participation of academic staff in training for academic staff development in tertiary institutions in Delta State

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study

1. What are the various training programmes for academic staff development in tertiary institutions in Delta State?
2. What are the perceived impact of training on academic staff in tertiary institutions in Delta State?
3. What are the relationship between sex and academic staff participation in training for academic staff development in tertiary institutions in Delta State?
4. What are the relationship between finance and academic staff participation in training for academic staff development in tertiary institutions in Delta State?

Hypotheses

Hypotheses tested are:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between sex and participation of academic staff in training for staff development in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between finance and participation of academic staff in training for staff development in tertiary institutions in Delta State

Methodology

This study adopted the descriptive design. The descriptive design was used in this study because it allowed the researchers to study the phenomena under focus by using a representative sample drawn from the population in investigating the training programmes for academic staff development from the academic staff in the tertiary institutions in Delta State.

The population of this study was made up of three thousand, one hundred and forty-five (3,145) academic staff of eleven tertiary institutions in Delta State (Federal University of Petroleum, Effurun; Nigerian Maritime Universities, Okerenkoko; Delta State University, Abraka; Dennis Osadebay University, Asaba; University of Science and Technology, Ozoro; University of Delta, Agbor; Delta State Polytechnic, Oghara; Delta State Polytechnic, Ogwashuku; Federal College of Education (Technical), Asaba; College of Education, Warri; and Delta State college of Education, Mosogar).

The sample for this study was made up of four hundred and seventy-two (472) academic staff of eleven Federal and State tertiary institutions in Delta State; which is 15% of the population of academic staff in each institution selected as respondents for the study. This study made use of a researchers constructed close-ended questionnaire titled Training for Academic Staff Development (TASD).

The instrument was subjected to face and content validity by an expert in Measurement and Evaluation. The comments and corrections were considered and incorporated into the final production of the instruments. In order to determine the reliability of the questionnaire, test re-test approach was adopted in determining the reliability of the instrument and it yielded an index of 0.81 indicating that the instrument was reliable. This was done by using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Statistics.

The research questions of the study were analysed using frequency, percentage, and mean score. The hypotheses formulated were tested using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Statistics since they all seek to test the relationship between two variables. They were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Where P value is less than 0.05, a hypothesis was considered significant and where it is greater than 0.05, it was considered not significant. A total of Four hundred and fifty-six (456) questionnaire were retrieved out of which twelve (12) were not

properly filled. The analyses were, therefore based on four hundred and forty-four (444) properly filled questionnaires.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the various training programmes for academic staff development in tertiary institutions in Delta State?

Table 1: Mean of Various Training Programmes for Academic Staff Development in Tertiary Institutions.

S/N	Items	Weighted Response	Mean	Remark
1.	Master Degree	1560	3.51	Agreed
2.	Doctorate Degree	1616	3.64	Agreed
3.	Fellowship Studies	1258	2.83	Agreed
4.	Staff Orientation	1444	3.30	Agreed
5.	Mentorship	1392	3.13	Agreed
6.	Seminar	1540	3.50	Agreed
7.	Workshop	1461	3.30	Agreed
8.	Conference	1562	3.52	Agreed

Criterion Mean: 2.50

Data in Table 1 shows that all the items met the criterion mean of 2.50 and were therefore agreed. This means that the various training programmes for academic staff development in tertiary institutions in Delta State are master and doctorate degrees, fellowship studies, staff orientation, mentorship, seminar, workshop and conference.

Research Question 2: What is the perceived impact of training on academic staff in tertiary institutions in Delta State?

Table 2: Mean Impact of Training on Academic Staff in Tertiary Institutions

S/N	Items	Mean	Remark
1.	Training programmes have improved my teaching skills	3.32	Agreed
2.	My research skills have improved through training programmes	3.31	Agreed
3.	Training has improved my interaction with students	3.22	Agreed
4.	Training programmes have impacted on my confidence during teaching	3.00	Agreed
5.	My interaction with colleagues have improved	3.01	Agreed

Criterion Mean: 2.50

Data in Table 2 shows that all the items met the criterion mean of 2.50 and were, therefore agreed. This means that training has impacted on academic staff in tertiary institution by improving their teaching and research skills, confidence during lectures and interaction with students and colleagues.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between sex and participation of academic staff in training for staff development in tertiary institutions in Delta State.

Table 3: Pearson r test of Relationship between Sex and Participation of Academic Staff in Training for Staff Development in Tertiary Institutions

Variables	n	Df	R.	P. Value	Decision
Sex	444	442	1.000	0.000	Rejected
Participation					

Data in Table 3 revealed that the r.cal is 1.000 and p value is 0.000. Since the p value is less than 0.05, the tested hypothesis is statistically significant, therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that there was a relationship between sex and participation of academic staff in training programme.

H_{02} : There is no significant relationship between finance and participation of academic staff in training for staff development in tertiary institutions in Delta State

Table 4: Pearson r test of Relationship between Finance and Participation of Academic Staff in Training for Staff Development in Tertiary Institutions.

Variables	n	Df	R.	P. Value	Decision
Finance	444	442	0.16	0.011	Rejected
Participation					

Data in Table 4 revealed that the r.cal is 0.16 and p value is 0.011. Since the p value is less than 0.05, the tested hypothesis is statistically significant, therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a relationship between finance and participation of academic staff in training programme.

Discussion of Findings

Findings from the study revealed that the various training programmes for academic staff development in tertiary institutions in Delta state are master and doctorate degrees, fellowship studies, staff orientation, mentorship, seminar, workshop and conference. This finding is supported by Oyigbenu (2020) who assessed the effect of employee training on performance of academic staff of some selected tertiary institutions in Nasarawa State and found that effective methods of staff training used in the institutions were workshops, seminars, conferences and in-service training which were suitable and effective. Oyitso and Olomukoro, (2012) also stated that lecturers need to work together through staff development programmes such as conferences, seminars, workshops, and study groups in areas of common interest in order to enhance their professional growth and competences. Similarly, Gutek (2017) explained that seminars, conferences and workshops are opportunities for meeting on

specialized subject area and often held in a day or more to discuss a topic of interest relevant to the organisation.

Secondly, finding from the study revealed that training has perceived impacted on academic staff in tertiary institution by improving their teaching and research skills, confidence during lectures and interaction with students and colleagues. This finding is supported by Oyigbenu (2020) who assessed the effect of employee training on performance of academic staff of some selected tertiary institutions in Nasarawa State and found that there is a significant relationship between training and employee's performance was also identified. Oyitso and Olowolaiyemo (2018) also investigated the role of continuing professional training in career development for women in Edo State and found that the types of training programme available for career women in organisations are computer appreciation, conference/workshop/seminars and in-service training and that the expected roles of continuing professional training programme on career women are to improve service delivery, enhance task performance, encourage employees' loyalty to organization and improve their productivity. Similarly, Ogbu, Ojo and Ozah (2018) found that staff training has a significant impact on academic staffs' productivity. It was also found that staff training has hugely enhanced academic staffs' timeliness in service delivery; and finally, staff training has a significant effect on academic staffs' work quality.

Thirdly, findings from this study revealed that there was a relationship between sex and participation of academic staff in training programme. This finding corroborated Alshorman and Bawaneh (2018) who assessed the attitudes of university faculty members on training for the use of the Learning Management System (LMS) in teaching and learning and showed statistically significant differences in the attitudes of university faculty members due to gender and in favor of the males. Similarly, Abd, Arumugam, Yahaya, Yaakob and Mohd (2015) reported a significant difference and positive attitude towards SDT based on gender. Anas, Heitham, Magda, and Mohamed (2019) also found that the males' researcher has not only published significantly more than females but also appeared to have significantly more years of research experience.

This agreement with these findings is seemingly influenced by the existential situation in the areas of study which seems to be in favour of the men. For instance, due to traditional roles of women as mothers and primary caregivers, it would be easier for a man to attend a training programme or conference in a distant community than it is for a woman especially if she has young ones in her care. This is because

she may want to consider their wellbeing as priority and until she is satisfied with whatever provision for she makes for their safety and wellbeing, attending a conference may be the least on her mind. This same is true of woman who is nominated impromptu to attend seminar, workshop or conference where she will be required to pass several nights. Secondly, security situations prevent even willing women from attending and participating in developmental programme. While this is equally true of the men, the willingness and tendency to withdraw from a programme scheduled to hold in security challenged destination may be higher among the women than the men.

Finally, findings revealed there was a relationship between finance and participation of academic staff in training programme. This finding corroborated MaacNab and Whitefield (2017) who conducted a research on the impact of finance on participation of employees in training and development activities in Universities in South Africa and revealed that participation in conferences, seminars, workshops and higher education was significantly affected by availability of funds. They also reported that sponsored programmes had more participation than those in which participants are required to pay. Similarly, Dearden, Fitzsimons and Wyness (2020) studied the impact of higher education (HE) finance on university participation in the UK and reported that the impact of upfront tuition fees had a small negative impact on participation among high income groups, while the package of reforms introduced had no impact on participation, largely because tuition fees were accompanied by large increases in loans and grants.

Finance is a very essential aspect of any training programme. It may not be out of place to say that training cannot take place without finance. This is because it is a basic requirement right from the conception of a training programme to its implementation. In several training programmes, the participation of trainees is tied to one form of financial expectations or the other and even when training is made free for participants, it is because someone has paid for it and rather not the absence of finance. So for individuals who are not financially buoyant, participating in training programmes may be limited to immediate environment or those in very close proximity.

Conclusion

Based on the findings from the study, it was concluded that training programmes designed for the development of academic staff include master's and doctorate degrees, fellowship studies, staff

orientation, mentorship, seminar, workshop and conference. These training programmes have potential for capacity development and improvement in the productivity level of academic staff. In addition, when training programme are tailored towards the needs of participants, they are capable of engaging and retaining interest of trainees which will result in high level of participation. In essence, the training programmes provided for academic staff of tertiary institutions is very significant for personal and institutional development and so necessary steps must be taken to planning and organizing it to ensure that academic staff gets the best out of it.

Recommendations

In view of the findings and conclusion arising from this study, the following recommendations are made

1. Management of tertiary institutions should sustain the training programmes for academic staff development while opening more opportunities for staff to access those training programmes which have little or no patronage.
2. Management of tertiary institutions should sustain the interest of academic staffs in training programme by involving them in training programme. Every member of staff should take turns to present papers on topics of interest during in-house capacity building sessions.
3. Organisers of training and developmental programmes can leverage on technology to enable those who may not be able to leave their homes for certain reasons to have access to the programme even from afar. This will help remove barriers towards participation.
4. Academic staff of tertiary institutions should include plans for training programmes in their annual budgets and provide for same. Management of tertiary institutions should encourage academic staff participation through financial and material support.

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